

D2.4: Second report on the status of the relationship with the EOSC Governance and the EOSC-related initiatives

Lead Partner:	INFN
Version:	V1.0
Status:	Submitted
Dissemination Level:	PU
Document Link:	https://repository.eosc-pillar.eu/index.php/s/6dywRGDs7DdE6CX

Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable describes the status of the relationship with the EOSC Governance and the existing projects/initiatives related to the EOSC and the foreseen synergies at two years from the project start.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Parties of EOSC-Pillar is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The EOSC-Pillar project is co-funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 programme under grant number 857650.

DELIVERY SLIP

	Name	Partner/Activity	Date
From:	Laura Perini	INFN/T2.2	07/06/2021
Reviewed by:	Jos van Wezel	KIT/WP3-WP4	18/06/2021
Reviewed by:	Sara Di Giorgio	GARR/WP4	18/06/2021
Reviewed by:	Philipp von Hartrott	Fraunhofer/WP5	18/06/2021
Approved by:	Fulvio Galeazzi		01/07/2021

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
V0.1	30/04/2021	Document Structure	Laura Perini (INFN)
V0.2	06/05/2021	Contribution on section 2.4	Lisa Honegger (UNIVIE)
V0.3	11/05/2021	Contribution on section 2.3	Sara Di Giorgio (GARR), Luciano Gaido (INFN), Federica Tanlongo (GARR)
V0.4	18/05/2021	Contribution on section 2.1	Tommaso Boccali (INFN)
V0.5	19/05/2021	Contribution on section 2.1	Federico Ruggieri (GARR)
V0.6	20/05/2021	Contribution on section 2.4	Laura Perini (INFN)
V0.7	20/05/2021	Contribution on section 2.4	Vincent Breton (CNRS)
V0.8	21/05/2021	Contribution on section 2.4	Jos van Wezel (KIT)
V0.9	01/06/2021	Finalization of section 1, 3,4 and of Executive Summary	Laura Perini (INFN)
V.091	03/06/2021	Contribution on section 2.1	Stefano Cozzini (Area Science Park)
V.092	04/06/2021	Contribution on section 2.1	Emma Lazzeri (GARR)
V0.93	04/06/2021	Contribution on section 2.4	Inge Van Nieuwerburgh (Gent University)
V1.0	25/06/2021	Revisions after internal review	Laura Perini (INFN)

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
AG	Advisory Group
CA	The Collaboration Agreement
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	EOSC Association
EOSC-Pillar	Coordination and Harmonisation of National and Thematic Initiatives to Support EOSC project
EOSC-Rel	Relationship of EOSC-Pillar with the EOSC Governance and the EOSC related initiatives
IG	Interest Group
NI	National Initiative
RoP	Rules of Participation
TF	Task Force
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

1	Context and Objectives of the EOSC-Rel	6
1.1	The EOSC-Rel Objectives	6
2	Work Performed in EOSC-Rel	7
2.1	The EOSC Working Groups as links to the EOSC Governance: EOSC-Pillar's participation and the results of the WG activities	7
2.2	The EOSC Association and EU Partnership: EOSC-Pillar's participation in the preparatory phase of 2020 and in the first half of 2021	17
2.3	Collaboration between the different INFRAEOSC05 Projects and with other EOSC Projects	24
2.4	The National Initiatives and the EOSC-Pillar role	30
3	Future perspectives in EOSC-Rel	37
4	Conclusions: Final Results and Impact	38

Executive summary

This document describes the relationship of EOSC-Pillar with the EOSC governance and the EOSC related initiatives (EOSC-Rel). We briefly describe how the EOSC was structured before the creation of the EOSC-Association and the main results achieved by the WG's that were established by the Executive Board of EOSC, which was a body of representatives from the research and e-infrastructures communities, appointed by the European Commission, with a mandate ending in December 2020. Then we describe the transition phase that has led to the present situation with the new EOSC-Association with its board of Directors, partner of the EC in the EU Partnership that is being established, together with the new Steering Board representing the Member States and Associated Countries. The setting up of the new Advisory Groups intended to complete and further develop the work of the previous WG's toward a fully valid EOSC is sketched and the role of EOSC-Pillar in the new structure of EOSC is shown.

The main aspects of the collaboration of EOSC-Pillar with the other projects, starting with the regional ones, are then described. The status of the National Initiatives supported by EOSC-Pillar in the countries where it is established is then briefly addressed.

Finally, we give an outlook of the EOSC-Rel activities in the near future and with the new incoming projects and conclude on the positive role played till now by EOSC-Pillar and the positive role expected for the EOSC future.

1 Context and Objectives of the EOSC-Rel

The EOSC model envisions a pan-European federation of data infrastructures built around a shared core. Its goal is providing access to a wide range of publicly funded services supplied at national, regional, institutional and thematic, i.e. horizontal, levels, and to complementary commercial services. Till the end of 2020 the governing bodies of the EOSC are the **Governance Board (GB)** and the **Executive Board (EB)**. The EB had established six Working Groups (WGs) as links with the interested parties and Member States. The description of the GB is available in <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-governance/eosc-governance-board>, and the description of EB in <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-governance/eosc-executive-board>.

WGs are also described in <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-working-groups>, but few lines are inserted in the following where the WG are discussed, for easier reading.

In the second half of 2020, the EOSC Association (EOSC-A) was started as AISBL under Belgian law (see <https://www.eosc.eu/#about>), more details are provided in section 2.2.

1.1 The EOSC-Rel Objectives

The objectives of EOSC-Pillar regarding establishing strong relationships with the governance and with the related projects are twofold: on the one hand, EOSC-Pillar wants to contribute to the groups that have been created. EOSC-Pillar aims at bringing in expertise, that was gained in previous projects and in the research activities pursued. On the other hand, EOSC-Pillar wants to stay informed about the discussed set of problems in all the groups and about the shared recommendations and solutions for EOSC implementation.

We think that the inputs EOSC-Pillar offers are important for the EOSC as they contribute to developing EOSC in ways that are most valuable for the communities and the regions EOSC-Pillar represents. To be more specific, we can mention the objectives:

- the EOSC to be of real use for the researchers, ensuring interoperability between scientific domains and across borders.
- the EOSC to help strengthen the Open European Data and Computing Infrastructure used by the researchers.

At the same time, it is important for EOSC-Pillar to follow closely the solutions proposed by the governance and the related bodies. Thereby, we are able to develop the project in ways that are most fruitful to the EOSC and suited for bringing the EOSC to a convergence of services and practices.

2 Work Performed in EOSC-Rel

The relations of EOSC-Pillar with the EOSC unfolds in three principal directions:

- The EOSC governance (both till 2020, and in the new configuration including EOSC-A)
- The other EOSC-related projects
- The National Initiatives in the different countries

The main links to the EOSC governance are provided by the structures established by the governance itself, in the first place by the EOSC Working Groups (WG).

2.1 The EOSC Working Groups as links to the EOSC Governance: EOSC-Pillar's participation and the results of the WG activities

The Governance Board together with the Executive Board has established EOSC priorities around which six EB Working Groups have been established.

- **Architecture**¹: Defining the technical framework required to enable and sustain an evolving EOSC federation of systems;
- **FAIR**²: Implementing the FAIR data principles by defining the corresponding requirements for the development of EOSC services, in order to foster cross-disciplinary interoperability;
- **Landscape**³: Mapping of the existing research infrastructures which are candidates to be part of the EOSC federation;
- **Rules of Participation**⁴: Designing the Rules of Participation that shall define the rights and obligations governing EOSC transactions between EOSC users, providers and operators;
- **Sustainability**⁵: Providing a set of recommendations concerning the implementation of an operational, scalable and sustainable EOSC federation after 2020.
- **Skills and Training**⁶: Providing a framework for a sustainable training infrastructure to support EOSC in all its phases and ensure its uptake.

The Working Groups form an official part of the EOSC Governance structure that will ensure a community-sourced approach to the current challenges of the EOSC.

All the Working Groups were handed over to the EOSC Association at the end of 2020, which took responsibility for the activities from 2021 onwards. Their outputs are valuable

¹ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/architecture-working-group>

² <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/fair-working-group>

³ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/landscape-working-group>

⁴ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/rules-participation-working-group>

⁵ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/sustainability-working-group>

⁶ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/skills-training-working-group>

inputs to the new Advisory Groups and in general have set the foundation of the EOSC concept.

In this Section, we describe the final results of the WG's obtained and point out the relevant contribution of EOSC-Pillar. We start recalling the participation in the WG's by EOSC-Pillar members: D. Vighetti, A. Ceccanti, M. Hardt, E. Ronchieri, J. Pansanel, P. Manghi, A. Streit, G. Polenta, P. Budroni, V. Beckman, F. De Pascalis, P. Pagano, F. Ruggieri, E. Lazzeri, R. Carrillo; this participation has been important not only in quantity, but also in quality, as many of the people we mention have important technical expertise useful for their specific WG. Moreover, in some of the EOSC-Pillar countries the discussions of the WG's were followed locally so that the EOSC-Pillar members were able to collect and bring in the WG's a larger feedback. In Italy, as an example, "Shadow Groups" were established where the EOSC-Pillar members who participated in the official WG's exchanged views and information with members of the National Initiative who had subscribed to the shadow group of their interest. Below at the end of the text describing each specific WG, we provide a brief indication of the EOSC-Pillar contribution.

2.1.1 Architecture

The EOSC Architecture Working Group has been active since mid-2019 through the end of 2020, with more than 50 members, mostly active, participating. A number of dedicated meetings have been organized, some of which as satellite meetings to larger events like EOSC Stakeholder Conferences. The rest of the activities, especially after the 2020 pandemic start, were followed via bi-weekly meetings.

The members were selected among the experts from the different countries, and from the EOSC projects already active at the moment of the working group definition. As such, they were representing the full spectrum of stakeholders and needs, thus providing a complete picture to the WG activities and a solid base on which to build the future EOSC.

Quite early, some essential components of the architecture were identified and considered wide enough to require dedicated task forces, which were promptly initiated via WG members and external experts. The Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure Task force (AAI-TF) and Persistent Identifier Tasks Force (PID-TF) were launched and were operational by the Fall 2019.

AAI and PID (persistent identifier) are essential blocks when building the EOSC as a system of systems, where existing e-Infrastructures are not disrupted when entering the EOSC, but are made cooperant using higher level slim services. AAI guarantees that national, project and external credentials and Single Sign On's (SSOs) can be used to access the EOSC in all its services, from portals, data services and thematic services. An EOSC-wide PID guarantees the capability to link data from different repositories, an added value which is one of the main reasons it is believed the EOSC can enrich European research by allowing the discovery of information from potentially all the continent level data sources.

The main outputs of those TFs were detailed reports on guidelines, directions and technical requirements, which have been incorporated in the [Architecture WG final reports](#)⁷.

⁷ <https://eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-architecture-wg-outputs>
www.eosc-pillar.eu

A third Task Force was launched later, in late Spring 2020, and dealt with research software, in its multiple aspects: accepted best-practices, the lifetime, the referencing and crediting, the description; this also delivered its final report.

The main contributions of the Architecture WG were in the preparation of large parts of EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), and of an additional [document on the Minimum Viable EOSC](#)⁸ (MVE), and in the [EOSC interoperability framework](#)⁹, all published by February 2021.

In particular, the SRIA is now the main input to the EOSC Advisory Groups, and contains a complete picture of the EOSC, including Guiding Principles, Implementation Challenges and Boundary Conditions.

The Minimum Viable EOSC is a subset of the final design, to be deployed by the end of the first EOSC phase, by 2023, in order to showcase capabilities and solutions.

The EOSC Interoperability Framework includes a clear picture of the minimum requirements for an effective EOSC, logging into its components, technical and organisational interoperability aspects.

The EOSC-Pillar members here stressed the importance of a viable EOSC already useful for the researchers and tailored to their needs, and of the resources, also in terms of computing infrastructures, necessary for a real use of the data.

2.1.2 FAIR

The EOSC FAIR Working Group was active from September 2019 through December 2020 and had the specific task to provide recommendations on the implementation of Open and FAIR practices within the EOSC.

The EOSC FAIR Working Group operated in close alignment with the Architecture WG to ensure that the FAIR principles of findability, accessibility, reusability and interoperability are supported by the technical arrangements under development. Two outcomes of the group were actually produced jointly.

The EOSC FAIR Working Group also collaborated with EOSC Landscape WG to ensure that the federation of relevant structures and initiatives is conducted under the scope of the FAIR principles.

The working group activated four different task forces:

- PID Policy
- FAIR Practice
- Interoperability
- Metrics & Certification

⁸ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/91fc0324-6b50-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1>

⁹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-190308283>

The main outcomes of the FAIR WG is the following list of official EU documents: for each document, we extracted and report below a short abstract, with the goal to provide a clear and concise overview of the work done within the WG. The full list of outputs is available at the [FAIR WG outputs](#)¹⁰ page.

[Six Recommendations for Implementation of FAIR Practice](#)¹¹

This document, produced by the FAIR practice task force analyses the state of FAIR practices within diverse research communities and FAIR-related policies in different countries and offers six practical recommendations on how FAIR can be turned into practice.

[A Persistent Identifier \(PID\) policy for the European Open Science Cloud](#)¹² - (in collaboration with EOSC Architecture WG)

This policy was authored by the PID task force of the EOSC FAIR Working Group and EOSC Architecture Working Group. This PID policy is written for senior decision makers within potential EOSC service and infrastructure providers and will be of interest to all EOSC stakeholders. It defines a set of expectations about what PIDs will be used to support a functioning environment of FAIR research. Requirements of providers and the basic services they offer are also outlined.

[Recommendations on FAIR Metrics for EOSC](#)¹³

The Recommendations on FAIR Metrics for EOSC document contains an analysis of activities relevant to the definition of FAIR Metrics in the EOSC context. It makes recommendations on the definition and implementation of metrics, proposes a set of metrics for FAIR data in EOSC to be extensively tested, offers an analysis of gaps and potential opportunities for extension, and defines priorities for future work.

[Recommendations on certifying services required to enable FAIR within EOSC](#)¹⁴

The Recommendations on certifying services required to enable FAIR within EOSC document contains an analysis of activities relevant to certification of the services required to enable FAIR research outputs within EOSC as of November 2020. It discusses incentivisation and support, offers an analysis of gaps and potential opportunities for extension, and defines priorities for future work. The FAIR Working Group of the EOSC Executive Board was initially tasked to define the certification approach that will be applied within EOSC for repositories that enable FAIR research outputs, but decided to expand the remit of their work to other services, because of the recognised need to define certification mechanisms for other elements of the FAIR ecosystem.

¹⁰ <https://eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-fair-wg-outputs>

¹¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/4630fa57-1348-11eb-9a54-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-166584930>

¹² <https://op.europa.eu/en-GB/web/eu-law-and-publications/publication-detail/-/publication/35c5ca10-1417-11eb-b57e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

¹³ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ced147c9-53c0-11eb-b59f-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-184008165>

¹⁴ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/70aa74b5-53bf-11eb-b59f-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-184009543>

[EOSC Interoperability Framework](#)¹⁵ - Official publication (in collaboration with EOSC Architecture WG)

This document has been developed by the Interoperability Task Force of the EOSC Executive Board FAIR Working Group, with participation from the Architecture WG. Achieving interoperability within EOSC is essential in order for the federation of services that will compose EOSC to provide added value for service users. In the context of the FAIR principles, interoperability is discussed in relation to the fact that “research data usually need to be integrated with other data; in addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing”. Our view on interoperability does not only consider data but also the many other research artefacts that may be used in the context of research activity, such as software code, scientific workflows, laboratory protocols, open hardware designs, etc. It also considers the need to make services and e-infrastructures as interoperable as possible. This document identifies the general principles that should drive the creation of the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF), and organises them into the four layers that are commonly considered in other interoperability frameworks (e.g., the European Interoperability Framework - EIF): technical, semantic, organisational and legal interoperability.

The contribution from EOSC-Pillar was particularly relevant in the EOSC Interoperability Framework, stressing the importance of considering the broad view of interoperability, that in the end was adopted in the document.

2.1.3 Landscape

The Landscape WG main results are the following documents, for which we provide a brief summary below: the full list of outputs is available at the [Landscape WG outputs](#)¹⁶ page

[Country Sheets Analysis](#)¹⁷

In this document, the Landscape WG surveyed and documented the landscape of infrastructures, initiatives, and policies across Europe relating to the development of the EOSC system. While the Landscape Report (see next point) summarised the existing policies and investments based on inputs provided by EU Member States, Associated Countries, and other countries (such as Azerbaijan, Belarus, Kosovo, and the UK), the Country Sheets Analysis goes several steps further. This document reflects the rapid development in the EOSC and delves deeper into the country sheet data, complementing the work being carried out by the INFRAEOSC-5B Projects, which are assessing the landscape at the local level.

[Landscape of EOSC-related Infrastructures and Initiatives version 2](#)¹⁸

¹⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-190308283>

¹⁶ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-landscape-wg-outputs>

¹⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/95e4a900-2a21-11eb-9d7e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-173316815>

¹⁸ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9c7f3c1e-2aea-11eb-9d7e->

This report describes activities in the Member States (MS) and Associated Countries (AC) related to EOSC, summarising existing policies and investments based on input from the MS and AC, the expert knowledge of the WG members and delegates to the EOSC Governing Board, as well as information from Horizon 2020 research projects and from open sources. The work builds on existing surveys and information provided by national authorities, stakeholder communities and the relevant H2020 projects in close collaboration with MS and AC. A [Validation Workshop](#)¹⁹ was held online in April 2020, to validate the provided contributions.

The EOSC-Pillar WP3, led by University of Vienna, had launched a “Landscape Survey” within the 5 countries of the project already in October-November 2019. For this purpose, four target groups (funding bodies, research infrastructures, e-infrastructures and universities) were defined and questions were tailored to each target group. 31% of the 2,204 invited representatives responded (in full or partially) to the questions. Not only the results of this activity, but notably also the methodology used at all stages, from design to the first analysis of the results, were a decisive contribution to the work of this WG.

2.1.4 Rules of Participation

The Rules of Participation WG main results are listed below, together with a short abstract: the full list of outputs is available at the [RoP WG outputs](#)²⁰ page.

[EOSC Rules of Participation](#)²¹

The Rules of Participation (RoP) for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) state the standards and conduct required of EOSC participants. EOSC participants agree to adhere to the RoP. Adherence to the RoP is expected to build trust in the EOSC and the resources accessible through EOSC. The RoP are based on the idea to develop quality through transparency and minimise the need for regulation. The rules themselves are high level in order to be generally applicable and long-lived.

- EOSC is based on the principle of openness
- EOSC resources align with FAIR principles
- EOSC services align with EOSC architecture & interoperability guidelines
- EOSC is based on principles of ethical behaviour and research integrity
- EOSC users are expected to contribute to EOSC
- EOSC users adhere to terms and conditions associated with the resources they use
- EOSC users reference the resources they use in their work
- Participation in EOSC is subject to applicable policies and legislation

01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-173604556

¹⁹ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/eosc-landscape-working-group-validation-workshop>

²⁰ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/rules-participation-working-group/eosc-rop-outputs>

²¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a96d6233-554e-11eb-b59f-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-184432576>

Ownership and evolution of the RoP from 2021 onwards²²

The RoP for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) underpin the policies, processes and procedures required to provide assurance of openness, quality and trust in the practices and services offered through voluntary participation in EOSC. The RoP were initially developed by the RoP WG during 2019-2020. This document proposes that the RoP are managed through a standing EOSC RoP Board that is established as an Operational or Advisory Body of the EOSC Association, under Article 6 of the Statues of the EOSC Association.

The EOSC-Pillar members stressed in particular the role of the users, according also to their past experiences in research performing organizations

2.1.5 Sustainability

The EOSC Sustainability Working Group was set-up to provide a set of recommendations concerning the implementation of an operational, scalable and sustainable EOSC federation after 2020, taking also in consideration a gradual open up of its user base to the public sector and industry. The final result of the activity has been published in the document “Solutions for a Sustainable EOSC - FAIR Lady report”. available at the [Sustainability WG outputs²³](#) page.

The activity started by producing a first document: “Solutions for a sustainable EOSC - Strawman report” and was then organized, internally to the WG, in four Task Forces:

- Strawman Feedback
- Business Model
- Legal Entities
- Integration of National Infrastructures

²² <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d96b59b8-70fd-11eb-9ac9-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-191673829>

²³ <https://eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-sustainability-wg-outputs>

Fig. 2.2.1 – Step by step process worked out in the preparation of the final document

The work proceeded in steps, with the examination of the feedback to the “Strawman” document leading to a “Tinman” document presenting an improved understanding of the possible business model for EOSC. A second feedback loop led to the production of the above-mentioned “Iron Lady” report.

Fig. 2.1.5.1 – Several synergies and contributions to the Iron Lady document

The model proposed in the “FAIR Lady” document is a stages process that starts with a Minimum Viable EOSC (MVE) graphically represented on the left side of the figure below, which includes the EOSC-Core and EOSC-Exchange components complemented by Federated Data.

Fig. 2.1.5.2 – EOSC Model with MVE

The WG examined suitable business models of EOSC, governance structures and legal entity. The analysis resulted in a set of strategic and financing orientations for EOSC in its second phase of implementation (post 2020). The activity also examined the impact of each legal and financial option to different stakeholders at national and European level.

Among the participants to this WG there was a significant number of members from organisations involved in the EOSC-Pillar project, which contributed to the results obtained by the WG. EOSC-Pillar contributions focused on the phase of the expanding EOSC, after the establishment of MVE, when engagement of a larger public sector and of private sectors will be required.

2.1.6 Skills and Training

This WG was created in January 2020 gathering together members nominated by the EOSC Governing Board. In February 2020 representatives from EOSC related projects were admitted to the WG through an open call. EOSC-Pillar Training task leader, Emma Lazzeri was admitted to join the group. The WG finally comprised 43 experts from a diverse European landscape, and aimed at identifying a framework for building competence and capabilities for EOSC.

Although the group could never meet in person because of COVID-19 pandemic outbreak, it was active until December 2020, and met frequently in conference calls, to discuss and deliver its final report [“Digital skills for FAIR and open science”](#)²⁴.

The WG focused on four priority areas that were discussed in distinct Task Forces:

1. Developing the next generation of FAIR and open science professionals.

This task force worked to define a framework describing the skills required to develop the next generation of FAIR and open science professionals, to maximise the uptake and utilisation of EOSC for all the EOSC actors (roles) in the EOSC ecosystem.

2. Collaborating to enhance digital skills for FAIR and open science in Europe.

This task force evaluated approaches that organisations at different levels use to implement their skills and training programmes to facilitate FAIR and open science within the EOSC ecosystem.

3. Building a trusted and long-lasting knowledge hub and related tools.

This task force reviewed current initiatives to consider the development of a federated EOSC catalogue for training resources as a means for creating a knowledge hub.

4. Influencing national open science policy for skills by supporting strategic leaders.

This task force investigated the placement of Digital Skills for FAIR and open science within national strategies with the goal to support EOSC implementation. The final study was commissioned to LDK²⁵ Consultants.

The task force working to define recommendations for a federated catalogue for training resources was chaired by EOSC-Pillar representative in the WG.

²⁴Manola, N., Lazzeri, E., Barker, M., Kuchma, I., Gaillard, V., Stoy, L., “Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science - Report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group”, European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. & EOSC Executive Board. Publication office (2021), <https://doi.org/10.2777/59065>

²⁵ <https://www.ldk.gr/index.php/en/>

The WG worked closely to the broader EOSC community and initiatives, from Member States and Associated Countries and Horizon 2020 EOSC projects, international research discipline communities and organisations.

The group collected inputs through interviews and surveys with target groups on specific issues and organized and joined several events to engage with the different EOSC stakeholders.

The WG engagement included presentations at the [EOSC Consultation Day](#)²⁶ - May 2020, participation at the [European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures \(ESFRI\) Research Infrastructures - EOSC Workshop](#)²⁷ - October 2020, and [EOSC Governance Symposium](#)²⁸ - October 2020.

The WG was invited to join a workshop organized by the INFRAEOSC-05 Task Force on Training and Skills in October 2020, “Workshop on Training Resources Catalogues Interoperability”, to exchange information and coordinating on important topics such as interoperability, quality and sustainability. This first workshop was followed by a second in April 2021, [“Workshop on Harmonising Training Resource Metadata for EOSC Communities”](#)²⁹ where the recommendations contained in the WG report were discussed, in particular the ones delivered around the realization of a federated catalogue for training resources.

The WG delivered a number of recommendations around the four main topics that were discussed in the 10 months of activities, that are summarized in the WG report.

The WG managed to deliver a Framework of Actors in the EOSC ecosystem that is a point of reference for initiatives, skills, training, reward and recognition frameworks and career paths necessary to support further development and mainstreaming of FAIR and open science.

The WG agreed on the need for coordinating and aligning relevant skills curricula and training frameworks by generating a consensus on a core European higher education curriculum to deliver FAIR and open science skills at university level, including proper qualifications.

One of the main recommendations of the WG was the need to support the competence centres approach as a framework for increasing coordinated provision of aligned training to support FAIR and open science.

The group also delivered specifications to build a learning and training catalogue that are needed to maximise interoperability.

²⁶<https://zenodo.org/record/3901388>

²⁷https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/Galeazzi_Session-3_ESFRI-EOSC_07.10.20.pdf

²⁸ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-symposium-2020-programme>

²⁹Newbold, Elizabeth, Kayumbi, Gabin, Whyte, Angus, &Lazzeri, Emma. (2021, May 21). Summary Report: Workshop on Harmonising Training Resource Metadata for EOSC Communities. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4769468>

The need to include learning and training resources in the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EIF) was highlighted by the WG together with the necessity to develop an EOSC Skills and Training Leadership Programme to:

- Increase coordination of European and national policies, programmes and networks supporting the skills elements of FAIR and open science.
- Develop and promote an EOSC Skills and Training Ambassadors programme to advise national decision makers.
- Advocate for the inclusion of skills and training of FAIR and open science into major European and national funding instruments.

The work done within the EOSC WG on Skills and Training is to be continued by the newly forming Advisory Groups (AGs) of the EOSC Association, in particular by the one focusing on research careers and curricula.

EOSC-Pillar contributions were especially relevant for the discussion on Competence Centres and on the learning and training catalogue as these structures are being implemented already in some of the EOSC-Pillar countries, thus providing direct experience. Continuity with the previous EOSC EB WG on Skills and Training is ensured also by the admission to participate to the Advisory Group of Emma Lazzeri, who is representing GARR in the “Upskilling countries to engage in EOSC” Task Force of the AG research career and curricula.

2.2 The EOSC Association and EU Partnership: EOSC-Pillar’s participation in the preparatory phase of 2020 and in the first half of 2021

The EOSC Association was established as a legal entity on 29 July 2020 with four founding members: GÉANT, represented by Cathrin Stover, CESAER - European Association of Universities of Technology, represented by Karel Luyben, CSIC for Spain, represented by José Luis de Miguel, and ICDI the Italian mandated organization, represented by Federico Ruggieri-GARR, who is also the coordinator of EOSC-Pillar, more details in 2.4. The representatives of the four founding members acted as non-statutory directors in the preparation of the first GA. The first General Assembly of EOSC-A was held on 17 December 2020, with 122 ordinary organizations, 22 mandated organizations and 48 observers (see EOSC Association Members³⁰). The GA elected the President, the Board of Directors³¹ and approved initial budget and fees. The GB is substituted by the Steering Board where all the Member States are represented by two persons nominated by the Ministry: the SB in these first year is configured as EC expert group.

It is worthwhile to note that the Vice-President of EOSC-A, Marialuisa Lavitrano, the most voted of the Directors, comes from the University of Milano-Bicocca which is one the

³⁰ <https://www.eosc.eu/members>

³¹ <https://www.eosc.eu/board-directors>

organizations participating in ICDI, the Italian mandated organization, supported by EOSC-Pillar.

2.2.1 The Partnership with EC for EOSC

The Association on June 23rd 2021 signed a Memorandum of Understanding with the European Commission to progress the EOSC partnership, which will bring together all relevant stakeholders to set-up the strategic planning of EOSC implementation under the Horizon Europe programme co-design and deploy a European Research Data Commons where data are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), and also as open as possible. Although the [MoU version](#)³² we can currently access is not yet final, still many points are stable enough and will be briefly summarized in the following:

2.2.1.1 General Objectives

- a) Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the ‘new normal’;
- b) Standards, tools and services allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results;
- c) Sustainable and federated infrastructures enable open sharing of scientific results.

2.2.1.2 Governance

The Partners will convene in the form of a Partnership Board as the main forum for dialogue and steering to reach the objectives set out in the Memorandum of Understanding. The Partnership Board will be co-chaired by the European Commission, represented by the lead service in charge of the European Partnership, and a co-chair from the Partners other than the Union, selected among their members nominated to the Partnership Board.

The Commission will systematically invite, to the meetings of the Partnership Board, representatives of a Steering Board composed of delegates from Member States and countries associated to the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, in order to ensure that national policies and investments relevant to the European Open Science Cloud are taken into account.

2.2.1.3 Activities and commitments of the Partners

The European Commission undertakes to duly take into account the input and advice from the Partners other than the Union when identifying and defining call topics for research and innovation activities in the scope of and linked to the Co-programmed partnership on the European Open Science Cloud to be included in the Horizon Europe Work Programmes. For this purpose, the European Commission undertakes to consult and maintain a regular dialogue with the Partners other than the Union during the

32

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/research_and_innovation/funding/documents/ec_rtd_he-partnership-open-science-cloud-eosc.pdf

preparation of the Work Programmes. The call topics will be subject to Horizon Europe comitology procedures.

Partners other than the Union will be reporting on:

- a) In-kind contributions to the actions funded by the Union
- b) In-kind contributions to the additional activities, foreseen in the Additional Activities Plan;
- c) Investments in operational activities foreseen beyond the SRIA, and leverage including other investment mobilised to exploit or scale-up partnership results.

At the level of the projects (point a), reporting will be done continually through European Commission's reporting systems for management of the Horizon Europe programme.

At the level of the partnership (points b and c), reporting will be done through annual or biennial reporting by the Partners

2.2.2 The Steering Board

The first meeting of the EOSC Steering Board (EOSC-SB) was held on 11 March 2021 via video conference. The meeting was attended by 44 representatives of the Member States and 13 participants from the European Commission (DG RTD and DG CNECT). During the meeting, the participants have been informed about the setting-up of the EOSC-SB Expert Group, its final Terms of Reference, the draft Memorandum of Understanding of the candidate EOSC European Partnership, as well as the relationship between the EOSC-SB and the new Expert Group on the ERA Forum for Transition. The two main subjects for discussion were the draft Rules of Procedure of the Board and its future Work Plan.

The second meeting was held on 8 April 2021, the main points decided being:

- The Commission will inform about options on the representation of the EOSC-SB in the ERA Forum for Transition in the next meeting;
- The EOSC-SB Rules of Procedure were adopted with the minor changes proposed by the Commission;
- One person from the EOSC-SB shall be elected to accompany one person of the Committee to the EOSC Partnership Board, and that this person will be invited to future Steering Committee meeting. The election will take place during the next EOSC-SB meeting;
- The Work Plan 2021 is adopted with the changes proposed during the meeting;
- The Chair to invite the EOSC Association as permanent Observer to the EOSC-SB (as per Work Plan);
- The prioritised policy issues will be the focus of a sub-group (named "sub-group A" until a more appropriate name is decided upon) As an outcome of the discussion, it was agreed to prioritise and focus on the policy issue concerning the benchmarking of (i) Member States EOSC-ready infrastructures and initiatives, including the regional activities supporting the EOSC, and (ii) the in-kind contributions and financing of EOSC relevant infrastructures and initiatives across countries. In addition, it was proposed that the two policy issues should be complemented with a focus on monitoring the

benefit of what EOSC brings to the EU and Associated Countries, including considering the various levels of readiness for in-kind contribution to the EOSC

The third meeting was held on 26 May 2021 with

- the Election of the SB Delegate and Alternate in the Partnership Board: Volker Beckman is elected as Delegate and Giorgio Rossi as Alternate
- the presence of the President and Vice-President (Marialuisa Lavitrano) of EOSC-A, for now on permanently invited, and presentation by Karel Luyben's of the status of EOSC-A
- The presentation by Volker Beckman (chair of sub-group A) of the status of its works
- The discussion of further policy issues in addition of sub-group A

EOSC-Pillar presence is effective also in the SB, e.g L. Perini (leader of task 2.2 in EOSC-Pillar, and Chair of ICDI) is the second Italian representative, while V. Beckmann (French representative) was involved in EOSC-Pillar from the beginning (WP7 leader before taking up his new role with the French Ministry) and G. Rossi has strong links with ICDI, the Italian NI.

2.2.3 The Advisory Groups of EOSC-A

EOSC-A is setting up Advisory Groups (AGs) that will provide advice on the fulfilment of the Association's mission and their outputs will contribute to the preparation of documents such as the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda and multi-annual roadmap. Directors are nominated to act as a liaison between AGs and the Board to ensure an effective two-way communication. The list of the AGs and of the Task Forces (TF) in which these are articulated is reported below with a brief explanation of their scope.

Implementation of EOSC Advisory Group

The Task Forces within this Advisory Group focus on rolling out EOSC recommendations and testing their applicability with research communities and service providers. They also seek to promote broader adoption of EOSC, specifically amongst the research community.

Rules of Participation compliance monitoring

This TF focuses on collecting feedback on implementing the Rules of Participation (RoP) to ensure they meet EOSC user and service provider needs, iterating where necessary. Advice may be needed to help transition the RoP into an implementable checklist. [Guidelines on the ownership and evolution of the RoP](#)³³ from 2021 were drafted which can guide work.

PID policy and implementation

³³ <https://doi.org/10.2777/67118>

This TF monitors and provides community feedback on the implementation of the [PID policy](#)³⁴ and [Architecture](#)³⁵. Further proposals for integration of services may be needed to implement and test the guidelines in full.

Researcher engagement and adoption

This TF focuses on engaging research communities to increase their participation in EOSC. Work will be conducted along disciplinary lines, utilising ESFRIs and thematic data services, as well as on a country basis via engaging research performing organisations, and by collaborating with representative bodies such as EURODOC, the Young Academy of Europe or Marie Curie alumni.

Technical challenges on EOSC Advisory Group

The Task Forces within this Advisory Group focus on implementing the technical architecture and interoperability in EOSC. They also provide a steer on strategic areas of future work, such as infrastructure for sharing research software.

Technical interoperability of data and services

This TF moves from the [EOSC Interoperability Framework](#)³⁶ recommendations around technical architecture to help develop the EOSC Core and Exchange. Activities will include engaging with the community to oversee the federation of thematic services and datasets and activities to advance the composability of resources.

Infrastructure for quality research software

This TF takes the recommendations of the [Scholarly Infrastructure for Research Software report](#)³⁷ and progresses them further. The nine participants to the SIRS report already operate infrastructure for software source code and are well placed to lead the group.

AAI implementation

This TF monitors and provides community feedback on the implementation of the [AAI Architecture](#)³⁸.

Metadata and data quality Advisory Group

The Task Forces within this Advisory Group focus on implementing the FAIR agenda. There is a particular focus on addressing semantic interoperability to ensure data can be discovered and reused, as well as aspects of data quality and metrics to promote high-quality resources in EOSC.

Semantic interoperability

³⁴ <https://doi.org/10.2777/926037>

³⁵ <https://doi.org/10.2777/525581>

³⁶ <https://doi.org/10.2777/620649>

³⁷ <https://doi.org/10.2777/28598>

³⁸ <https://doi.org/10.2777/8702>

This TF takes the [EOSC Interoperability Framework](#)³⁹ recommendations around metadata and semantics, in particular advancing work and building consensus on a minimum metadata framework for EOSC. Recommendations from the [Implementation of FAIR practice](#)⁴⁰ report could also be addressed to support communities which have not yet established standards.

FAIR metrics and data quality

This TF oversees the implementation of the [FAIR metrics for EOSC](#)⁴¹, testing them with research communities to ensure they are fit for purpose. Aspects of data quality should also be considered so the data available within EOSC is robust and highly regarded by communities.

Research careers and curricula Advisory Group

The Task Forces within this Advisory Group focus on the training and skills agenda. Multiple stakeholder groups are addressed, specifically research communities, data stewards and national bodies.

Data stewardship curricula and career paths

This TF builds on activities to define data stewardship curricula to ensure these are recognised and aligned across Europe. Attention will also be paid to career paths to ensure appropriate recognition and rewards for data management activities. Recommendations from the [Digital Skills for FAIR and Open Science](#)⁴² report will be taken forward by this group.

Research careers, recognition and credit

In parallel with the data stewardship TF, this group will address incentives for researchers to manage and share their data, code and other research outputs. This could include criteria on Open Science and FAIR being part of selection and promotion criteria, funders and governments requiring examples of data/code sharing as part of assessment exercises, or data prizes.

Upskilling countries to engage in EOSC

This TF recognizes the significant developments in Open Science education being addressed at Member State level within research performing organisations and disciplinary groups. It will assist in aligning skills initiatives and supporting the onboarding of these into EOSC. The group will also promote the exchange of models across the groups.

Sustaining EOSC Advisory Group

³⁹ <https://doi.org/10.2777/620649>

⁴⁰ <https://doi.org/10.2777/986252>

⁴¹ <https://doi.org/10.2777/70791>

⁴² <https://doi.org/10.2777/59065>

The Task Forces within this Advisory Group focus on sustaining EOSC by developing appropriate funding models and promoting long-term preservation so data and services remain available.

Defining funding models for EOSC

A clear funding model has not yet emerged to address the challenges of costing and delivering services across national and community borders. This TF should progress recommendations from the [FAIR Lady](#)⁴³ report to help develop and test workable models. The TF will be composed of a wide range of service providers with diverse business models, including publicly funded providers.

Long-term preservation

This TF addresses long-term access to the resources available within EOSC by exploring a network of trusted and sustainable digital repositories. Recommendations from the [report on data preservation in the context of EOSC](#)⁴⁴ as well as [certifying services required to enable FAIR within EOSC](#)⁴⁵ will be taken forward by this group.

Working principles for Advisory Groups

- Research community representatives should be part of all AGs to ensure the EOSC infrastructure and services meet their needs
- EOSC Association members & observers should be the primary members of AGs
- Representatives of the key implementation projects should be members of relevant AGs to present work in progress and receive advice and steers from the community
- The ideas and priorities of the EOSC Association Advisory Groups should feed into the Descriptions of Work of the upcoming Horizon Europe projects
- Activities of the AGs should be visible to the wider community via blogs, webinars, email updates, recommendations and outputs
- Cross AG communication should be facilitated as remits will inevitably overlap

The AGs have now concluded the process of drafting their detailed charters and more than 250 have already volunteered for this work : however a new call for contributors will be issued soon.

The participation of EOSC-Pillar members to the AG's is active and important: if we concentrate on the coordinators that prepared the charters of the TFs, we see that out of a total of 52 coordinators (4 for each TF) 9 come from institutions that are participating in the EOSC-Pillar project, and five more come from institutions that are participating in ICDI, the Italian mandated organization, supported by EOSC-Pillar.

⁴³ <https://doi.org/10.2777/870770>

⁴⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4574234>

⁴⁵ <https://doi.org/10.2777/127253>

2.2.4 The role of EOSC-Pillar in this initial phase of EOSC-A

From the above description and from the people involved in the different boards/initiatives it is clear that EOSC-Pillar is playing a very relevant role in the structure of the EOSC as set up from the start of EOSC-A: as detailed above this was true for the transition phase that led to the establishment of EOSC-A, it is true for the current phase, both as presence in the coordination of the TF in which the AGs are articulated and as role in the EOSC-A management. The presence of EOSC-Pillar people is also important at the level of Steering Board.

2.3 Collaboration between the different INFRAEOSC05 Projects and with other EOSC Projects

2.3.1 INFRAEOSC05 Projects

The projects supported by the INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019 call (Call5), i.e., EOSC-Synergy, EOSC-Pillar, EOSC Nordic, NI4OS-Europe, ExPaNDS, FAIRsFAIR, and EOSCSecretariat.eu signed a [Collaboration Agreement 'Support to the EOSC Governance'](#)⁴⁶ at the end of December 2019. The Agreement provides a Joint Activity Plan, which guides the projects through the synchronisation and coordination of activities, avoiding overlaps, creating Task Forces dedicated to address common activities and finally developing a common strategy to synchronise activities with the EOSC Executive Board WGs and other EOSC initiatives (see [EOSC-Pillar deliverable D2.3](#)⁴⁷): e.g., EOSC hub and EOSC-Enhance).

The Joint Activity Plan and the underlying strategy is revised every six months by the coordination board, a board including two delegates from the seven projects' management. Revisions include the number and scoping of the activities to be carried out, both in the form of creating new task forces or closing others that may have achieved their objective or be no more relevant, or revising the work plan of a given task force. Changes can be proposed by the board members themselves or stem from the thematic Task Forces' activities and developments. This mechanism was envisaged to make sure that the activities carried out in the task forces are in line with the evolutions happening in the projects' work plans and strategies as well as in the wider EOSC scenario.

Six Task Forces (TFs) have been created to discuss and provide solutions for commonly identified issues and challenges in building EOSC:

1. Landscaping;
2. FAIR data and infrastructure;
3. Service Onboarding;
4. National Policies and Governance;
5. Training and Skills

⁴⁶ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/working-together-eosc-collaboration-agreement>

⁴⁷ Internal link: <https://repository.eosc-pillar.eu/index.php/apps/files?dir=/EOSC-Pillar%20Shared%20Files/Deliverables%20and%20Milestones/Deliverables&fileid=1532#pdfviewer>

6. Communications and Events.

Their distinguishing characteristic is the strict link with the work done at the national and regional level, characterised by specific policies, operational products, and established priorities. In some cases, these TFs have extended the collaboration also to other initiatives and projects.

According to the Joint activity plan, presented in D2.3, the six Task Forces worked closely with the support of the EOSC Secretariat.eu, on identified topics to address common activities. A short description of the TFs and their main activities is given below.

2.3.1.1 *Landscaping TF*

The Landscaping Task Force, chaired by GARR, EOSC-Pillar coordinator, has worked in close collaboration with the Landscaping Working Group (WG) to provide input to the Landscape report for the countries and infrastructures/activities involved in the regional projects. This has been done through the participation of project experts in some of the WG meetings, as well as through the organisation of dedicated meetings with the WG chair, and the revision of documents and materials.

The WG was also involved in the discussion to define the methodology of the various surveys carried out by the projects regarding National Initiatives (NI) so as to obtain structured and comparable data for each country. This was one of the first problems the projects (the four regionals in particular) tackled soon in their lifetime, even before the formal establishment of the TF: all regionals had NI survey activities somehow covered in their work plans but the challenge was to make them as comparable as possible.

EOSC-Pillar made available their methodology, questions and even the questionnaire code to the partners, which helped mitigate this issue, however a consultant was hired to compare the results ex-post as a part of the co-creation effort in EOSC Secretariat.eu. A comprehensive report including the data from all the regional surveys was published ([EOSC: Landscaping analysis](#)⁴⁸).

Besides coordinating the landscape surveying activities in the different projects, the TF actively animated the discussion on moving from a static landscape to living sets of indicators to monitor the progresses towards EOSC, that are able to guarantee a constant update of the situation given that EOSC is a process, and evolving very rapidly, too. Thanks to the collaboration and insightful discussion with the Landscape WG and other stakeholders we elaborated a [Working Proposal for Living Indicators to Monitor MS Progresses towards EOSC Readiness](#)⁴⁹. The initial list of indicators was presented and discussed at a dedicated EOSC-Pillar-organised workshop on 'National Policy Developments Supporting EOSC Implementation' co-located with the EOSC-hub Week on 20 May 2020, where the first round of feedback was gathered and incorporated in the document. Then a more focussed consultation, mainly addressing GB delegates, WG delegates and NII/RI representatives was carried out by the TF. All-in-all around 200 people were involved between the two

⁴⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/4683278>

⁴⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/4312793>

rounds of interaction, plus the internal feedback from our project colleagues. The set of indicators were discussed and approved by the [Landscape WG final validation workshop](#)⁵⁰ (28-29 September 2020) and are presented in the [second report of Working Proposal for Living Indicators to Monitor MS Progresses towards EOSC Readiness](#)⁵¹. To move forward, the TF has set up a plan to realize a dashboard to monitor live indicators to measure EOSC readiness of MS, gathering automatic and non-automatic data collection at country level.

The dashboard project proposal, as a Proof of Concept, was submitted in response to a EOSC Secretariat.eu co-creation call closed on 2 December 2020, and it has been approved. EOSC-Pillar T4.2 is coordinating the development of the dashboard's PoC, which includes:

- the selection and hiring a consultancy firm that will use the initial list of indicators and related metrics defined by the Landscaping Task Force to design the dashboard and select an open-source tool to implement it;
- define the workflows for the automatic and non-automatic data collection from NI;
- define processes for practically implementing the active monitoring, reporting and analysis of progress against the indicators, including user guidelines;
- define mechanisms to ensure the transparency, accountability and actionability of the collected information;
- ensure flexible solutions to update and develop new indicators;
- identify use-cases to test and refine the workflow to gather the information.

2.3.1.2 FAIR data and infrastructure

The task force, chaired by DANS (Data Archiving and Network Services, the Dutch national centre of expertise and repository for research data) and FAIRsFAIR project, reviewed the FAIR practices and guidelines for services and repositories produced by the regional projects. EOSC-Pillar's activities were based on integration of (existing) tools for FAIR research data providers into the Federated FAIR Data Space (F2DS), a data repository compliant service where metadata of different data sets is ingested and aligned for the benefit of researchers and data managers. The project also contributed to the discussion on common metadata and ontologies, and shared its experiences about its helpdesk service and training and documentation on FAIR tools and FAIR data. Upon request from the European Commission, the TF organised on Thursday 26th of November 2020 a workshop to present the initial finding about [FAIR data assessment and certification: challenges, lessons learned and recommendations from the InfraEOSC-5 projects](#)⁵². The meeting also gave a deep-dive into practical use cases that demonstrate the impact of applying the current tools to different communities across Europe and the priorities for the stakeholders involved. Jos van Wezel (KIT), presented EOSC-Pillar activities and tools.

EOSC-Pillar exchanged the [“Legal and Policy Framework and Federation Blueprint”](#)

⁵⁰ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/events/eosc-landscape-final-validation-workshop>

⁵¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/4452799>

⁵² <https://zenodo.org/record/4486280>

deliverable⁵³ that assesses the legal constraints hindering the full development of Open Access and Open Science principles, and highlights the impact of such constraints on the successful participation of EU Member States in EOSC services enabling multinational FAIR data. The TF will analyse the EOSC-Pillar guidelines to support researchers in publishing, sharing and integrating data, thus guaranteeing the openness with the goal of promoting the FAIR principles beyond their original scope.

2.3.1.3 Service Onboarding

The goal of the TF, initially chaired by NI4OS-Europe and then by EOSC-Pillar, is to disseminate the EOSC portal procedures to the regional projects, in coordination with EOSC-Enhance and EOSC-hub (and then EOSC Future) to make the different catalogues and onboarding procedures interoperable. Although the projects funded within the INFRAEOSC-05b call developed different models for regional catalogues (or registries), interoperation with the EOSC central catalogue is a common need and has been recognized as the main area for a joint activity. The Task force had a constant dialogue with the team involved in the EOSC Portal development (EOSC-Enhance) and in the onboarding operations (carried out by the so-called EOSC Portal Onboarding Team - EPOT) to inform the Call5 projects about the new features of the Portal, such as the API features and the changes in the procedures as well as the channels to provide feedback and get thorough technical information.

EOSC Pillar has triggered the discussion on the definition of guidelines to support the onboarding procedures and workflows for the national catalogues operators, based on the existing ones either at EOSC level or within the regional projects. The different validation criteria and procedures have been analysed in order to understand how to achieve compatibility among the EOSC catalogue and the national ones. This aspect will be presented in the guidelines for the national catalogues operators which will be released by EOSC-Pillar by June 2021. On this subject, EOSC-Pillar is co-organising the workshop “Incorporating National Service and Resource Catalogues into the EOSC” which foresees the participation of representatives of the other regional projects. Representatives of the other regional projects as well as of EOSC-Enhance and EOSC Future have been included in the organizing committee. The workshop is expected to be held before summer 2021.

2.3.1.4 National Policies and Governance

The Task Force, chaired by EOSC Secretariat.eu and KIT (organisation member of EOSC-Pillar) aims to exchange knowledge on open science policies and their implementation in the countries and organisations represented by the partners of the INFRAEOSC-05 projects. The TF has looked for commonalities and intersections throughout its existence and has contributed to identify shared progress indicators, taken further by the Landscaping TF and exchanged project internal progress and actions. A joint action plan has been discussed continuously and it was felt that the team and the collaboration in the TF is especially needed

⁵³ <https://zenodo.org/record/4486610>

once the components from the different AG (in which members of the policies TF are participating as well), will be set up. Therefore, the output from the TF will increase in parallel with the activities of the Association. The TF agrees on the need to work on harmonisation of projects regarding national policies, which is also planned for 2021. Finally, the plan is to cooperate on events related to policies organised by the contributing projects. The TF could potentially coordinate on dissemination and events activities and on recommendations to the Association and plans to do so in the coming months. The latest documents issued by the Association, e.g. SRIA, which came out during the last months, are the point of reference of the ongoing and future activities. The Task Force will continue to analyse this material and provide feedback. The members of the TF agree that at this moment it is strategic to invest energy in developing and implementing clear and shared policies, which take into account the problems based on legislation and propose guidelines with operational solutions to solve them. In this regard EOSC-Pillar project is contributing with the study performed in the EOSC-Pillar deliverable [D4.1 'Legal an policy framework and federation blueprint'](#)⁵⁴, that includes the legal and policy state of the art in the involved countries, which highlights commonalities to be leveraged and identifies gaps or challenges to be tackled in order to help harmonise and improve the national policies and strategies related to FAIR data and Open Science; drafted recommendations for policymakers concerning the rules and procedures with respect to legal issues regarding open access and open data as well as for services management, with a focus on the management of service level agreements.

2.3.1.5 Training and Skills

The Task Force is chaired by GARR, the coordinator of EOSC-Pillar project, and its aim is to set up a strategy for collaboration and sharing of results and best practices. So far, the following projects have showcased their approach and methodology: FAIRsFAIR, Synergy and EOSC-Pillar.

The Task force planned and organised a lot of events for the broader EOSC community dealing with training and skills related activities:

- 5 September 2020: ESOF session “I want to be an Open Scientist! Research Evaluation and Incentives to boost Open Science and Research Careers”. The format included mini-TED from expert speakers to introduce the debate and audience contribution via Mentimeter interactive tool. Themes for discussion included: Research evaluation, incentives, and rewards in the open science era, skills for the career programme with focus on data steward and policies for implementing open science. The session allowed for a good interaction, and the audience showed a lot of interest in the topic related to the paradigm change of research evaluation and career assessment.
- 29 October 2020: Training Catalogue interoperability Workshop. On a FAIRsFAIR proposal, a workshop was organised to discuss the theme of training catalogue interoperability. Given the attention around training catalogues being developed at disciplinary, thematic and national/regional level, and the interest in realising an EOSC

⁵⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/4486610>

federated catalogue for training resources, which was also reflected by the creation in June 2020 of a dedicated Task Force within the EOSC EB WG on Skills and Training, the Task Force organised a Workshop gathering together representatives of the main initiatives and projects involved.

- 14 April 2021: Workshop on Harmonising Training Resource Metadata for EOSC Communities. This workshop was organized as a follow up of the previous event on Training catalogue interoperability. The goal of the event was to plan joint action by current EOSC projects for a pilot to address recommendations in the report of the EOSC Working Group on Training & Skills, identifying issues and decisions to be taken on 'priority areas' selected.

The EOSC-Pillar training team is planning a set of pilot courses on Open Science practices within a specific domain, to be jointly organised with the reference Research Infrastructure. This new paradigm led to the organisation of two series of events to cover, as pilot projects, the Italian communities in the fields of Health and Earth and Environmental Sciences. To this aim, two sets of events were organised in conjunction with ELIXIR and EPOS respectively. Italy was chosen as the country of the pilot project, but all event series materials were developed in English to be easily reused by EOSC-Pillar trainers in the other countries covered by the consortium. The pilot projects also supported the start-up of the Italian Competence Centre task force within ICDI, as they highlighted the need to map and group the national experts in OS and EOSC related fields at national level, with the aim of coordinating efforts towards training and support initiatives in the Country.

The Task Force is focusing on common training paths targeted at cultivating EOSC-related skills, relying on existing material and expertise, and work on a shared catalogue of training resources.

2.3.1.6 *Communication and Events*

The Task Force, chaired by EOSC-Pillar until November 2020, aims to foster alignment on EOSC branding guidelines and activities of EOSC governance. It encourages mutual promotion and distribution of news, events and results of other projects in the CA through websites and social media channels and supports collaboration at events such as workshops and conferences.

To communicate the aim of the joint collaboration a video was released in September 2020 and it is available on [EOSC-Pillar YouTube channel](https://youtu.be/wy2sFUINxXw)⁵⁵.

On 5 September 2020, the Task Force in collaboration with EOSCSecretariat.eu, organised an interactive session that aimed at co-create the European Open Science Cloud, stepping from the Stakeholder Community needs. The discussion highlighted the need to shift the research evaluation system in Europe in order to produce quality and reliable data, to set up a working incentive system for individual researchers and organisations is one of the keys

⁵⁵ <https://youtu.be/wy2sFUINxXw>

to the widespread uptake of Open Science and FAIR practices. The slides of the presentations are available on the [EOSC-Pillar Zenodo community](#)⁵⁶.

Technical and content support was provided to the FAIR TF for the closed workshop with the European Commission in November 2020.

The TF is working on a series of coordinated interviews with respective ambassadors selected by each project. The interviews highlight the importance of FAIR data in scientific research and the potential benefits of a federated EOSC to their respective research activities, fields and regions or countries.

The projects are also collaborating to deliver a series of coordinated interviews with the EOSC Association Board of Director members. Interviews have been distributed according to geographical coverage of the projects. EOSC-Pillar has produced interviews with Klaus Tochtermann, Suzanne Dumouchel and Marialuisa Lavitrano.

The TF plans to also work on common “user personas” based on the outputs of the EOSC Training & Skills WG.

Several of the TF projects are launching “testimonial campaigns” to promote the European Open Science Cloud at the national level across researchers and research-performing organisations, these efforts will then be further publicised by EOSC Secretariat.eu. In this context, EOSC-Pillar is about to launch its Ambassadors Programme.

The Task Force plans to collaborate on the promotion of the EOSC Symposium 2021, which will be a key stage for all the projects involved.

2.3.2 Other EOSC Projects

EOSC-Pillar has collaborated with EOSC-Enhance and EOSC-Hub, with foreseen continuation in EOSC-Future. The bulk of these activities is taking place in the context of the Service Onboarding TF described in the previous section 2.3.1, and are dealt with above, in the description of the Service Onboarding TF.

2.4 The National Initiatives and the EOSC-Pillar role

As detailed in 2.2 the EOSC-A reserves a special role to the Mandated Organizations which are National Initiatives (NI) that receive by the Governments the mandate of representing the countries in EOSC.

EOSC-Pillar has a specific task (T4.3 Consolidation of National Initiatives) that is devoted to supporting such NIs, and has also set up a Transversal TF for capturing and exchanging between the different countries participating to the Project the information about their NI. The support of EOSC-Pillar is thus available in many different ways and is much appreciated by the NIs.

⁵⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4031170>

In the following, the status and perspectives of the NI in the countries participating in EOSC-Pillar are briefly described

2.4.1 Austria

The mandate to represent Austria in the EOSC Association lies with the “ACONET Verein” (related to the Austrian Academic Computer Network, the national research and education network) which is composed of various research performing institutions and research infrastructures in the country. To coordinate and carry out EOSC activities on a national level, the community is currently establishing an additional EOSC Support Office as the operational unit of the Austrian Mandated Organisation. This EOSC Support Office and its bodies, committees and working groups will be aligned with the structure of the EOSC Association to allow for integration of activities between European and Austrian efforts.

EOSC-Pillar is involved in the building of the EOSC Support Office Austria and supports these activities. A Memorandum of Understanding will serve as the basis of cooperation between all participating partners. EOSC-Pillar is supporting the process to establish this MoU and is involved in the working groups to design the set up and the operation of this office. The activities of this Support Office will include amongst the general coordination of EOSC and Open Science efforts, the continuous landscaping and monitoring of developments on the national level. The EOSC-Pillar National Initiatives Survey, conducted in 2019 and published in 2020, serves as valuable input to the identification of partners and stakeholders. It also delivers useful insights into the e-infrastructure landscape, as well as an overview over the policy landscape and funding regulations. Another important contribution of EOSC-Pillar to the development of the Austrian Mandated Organisation is the project’s contribution with regard to stakeholder engagement. The EOSC-Pillar partner institution UNIVIE (University of Vienna) has identified EOSC, Open Science and FAIR data as high priority areas. Thus, working groups for EOSC, data stewardship and the implementation of a research data management policy have been established. In addition, EOSC “Reference Points” are established at all partner institutions, to have a visible EOSC contact at all major research performing organisations and research infrastructures. The Austrian EOSC-Pillar project partners will establish this Reference Point at the University of Vienna, the largest university of the country, in close cooperation with the EOSC Secretariat.eu partners from the Technical University of Vienna.

The landscaping activity of EOSC-Pillar will be aligned to fit the needs of the Mandated Organisation and further links are established to engage the Austrian Mandated Organisation and its Support Office with other EOSC projects and activities (especially for consultation).

The stakeholder engagement activities of EOSC-Pillar, especially the ones on the national level, will also be incorporated into the coordinated efforts of the Austrian Initiative, as it is planned that the Support Office will become the single point of information for EOSC on a national level and will also be responsible to interact with all relevant stakeholders.

Another Austrian initiative, the “EOSC Café”, an open forum for EOSC, will also be aligned with the Support Office, in order to allow a connection to the EOSC Association Governance. The EOSC Café is coordinated by the former Austrian GB member and the current Austrian

representative in the Steering Group of the EOSC Association. This open forum serves mainly as information exchange and additional, larger network with regard to the European Open Science Cloud and includes representatives from the ministries, funding bodies, university and non-university research performing organisations and research infrastructures. EOSC-Pillar is also involved in and actively contributes to this national EOSC network.

2.4.2 Belgium

Belnet was selected by the Interministerial Conference for Science Policy, Belspo, as the mandated organisation for Belgium. As a National Research and Education Network (NREN), Belnet is one of the few research-oriented infrastructures in Belgium that is national in scope. Belnet has an important role to play as a service provider with services focussed on connectivity and security. They stimulate the deployment of the knowledge and information society by providing and maintaining high quality innovative network infrastructures with associated services. They meet the specific needs of higher education, researchers and government departments in Belgium through their expertise, unique position in the market and economies of scale. Belnet will represent the interests of all players that form a part of the Belgian research landscape. Furthermore, Belnet will take care to provide a variety of value-added services that EOSC can make use of.

Since Belgium is a federated country where research is a regional capacity, coordination is established through the Open Science working group of CIS-CFS (Commission International Cooperation-Commission Federal Cooperation). This working group consists of representatives of the different governments and Belgian Open Science experts. In the scope of this working group, a separate group is established to give a platform for discussion between Belgian EOSC members, the mandated organisation and the governments.

In Flanders, Belnet aligns with FOSB, the Flemish Open Science Board, established by the Flemish government to coordinate Open Science in Flanders in connection with European engagements. FRIS (Flanders Research Information Space) plays an instrumental role in connecting Flemish research to EOSC. FRIS (Flanders Research Information Space) is the regional portal on researchers and their research in Flanders. The Flemish Government wants to offer a unique window on research in Flanders and increase its visibility. FRIS will make the link with EOSC for Flanders.

In the Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles, Belnet aligns with the Open Science working group, which advises policy and organises dialogue between stakeholders.

To date, five universities became member of the EOSC-A. The rector's conference of Flanders, VLIR, and of the French speaking community, CREF, are observers as well as the Flemish funder FWO.

Already in November 2019 the governments organised an EOSC focussed event to bring together working group members, the delegate in the governance board and the different Belgian participants in EOSC related projects. The main objective of this seminar was to promote exchanges between all Belgian partners in EOSC projects and the Executive Board Working Groups.

Belgian organisations and research institutions have been and are involved in over 17 EOSC related projects (EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Future, EOSC-Life, EOSC-Hub...). Through Elixir, a collaboration between a number of ESFRIs in the life-sciences research landscape is set up to find synergies, broker collaborations and facilitate access to resources in the areas of data management and data analysis. This will allow to build expertise and knowledge across ESFRIs, expedite adoption of HPC cloud resources by other scientific domains and allow ESFRIs to provide services to their communities within the context of the EOSC. EOSC also presents an opportunity to implement Belgian projects in onboarding services, such as FAIR-GNSS, a project that aims to create a new, modern open data portal for European and Belgian GNSS data collections, built upon FAIR guiding principles.

2.4.3 France

France has been actively involved in the construction of the European Open Science Cloud from its beginning. French organizations have been involved in many European projects that have contributed to laying EOSC foundations, while French representatives have contributed actively to the different EOSC workings groups and boards.

At the national level, the [first workshop dedicated to EOSC](#)⁵⁷ was organized at CNRS in January 2020, followed by an [EOSC workshop](#)⁵⁸ involving all EOSC relevant partners in France organized by the French Ministry of Research, Higher Education and Innovation (MESRI) in February 2021. Year 2020 was dedicated to promoting EOSC in the research communities, structuring the French national initiative and organizing its representation in the EOSC governance bodies under the coordination of MESRI.

France represents 18 out of the 138 members of the EOSC association and 9 out of its 49 observers. The organization mandated to vote on behalf of France is INRIA (Institut National de Recherche en Informatique et Automatique).

24 French organizations including research organizations (BRGM, CNRS, IFREMER, INRAe, INRIA, INSERM) and universities (Univ. Aix-Marseille, Univ. Sorbonne, Univ. Versailles,...) are or have been participating to more than 30 European projects directly relevant to EOSC construction.

EOSC is identified as a cornerstone of [French National Plan for Open Science](#)⁵⁹ that aims at generalizing open access to publications and structure the opening of scientific data in a sustainable, European and international environment.

The management of EOSC-France will be entrusted to a collegium acting under the supervision of the national Digital Services and Infrastructures Committee (CoSIN). This collegium role is to coordinate and influence EOSC-France efforts, to inform and exchange with scientific communities about EOSC, and to ensure a strong French participation in EOSC related calls of the Horizon Europe work program. Because this collegium is not going

⁵⁷ <https://in2p3.cnrs.fr/fr/evenement/journee-eosc-au-cnrs>

⁵⁸ <https://eoscfrance.sciencesconf.org/>

⁵⁹ <https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/cid132529/le-plan-national-pour-la-science-ouverte-les-resultats-de-la-recherche-scientifique-ouverts-a-tous-sans-entrave-sans-delai-sans-paiement.html>

to be a legal entity it will not become a member of the EOSC Association, but its role will be to propose the next mandated member representing France at the EOSC Association.

2.4.4 Germany

In Germany, several initiatives work on the development of data federations and are in that respect related to EOSC. Some of them are still in starting up and concentrate on the organisation of internal and local affairs first. However, all have recognised the importance of EOSC, proven by their missions and statements issued. The German commitment to EOSC by German policy makers was demonstrated by the chair of the former EOSC Governance Board (2019-2020) which was held Dr. Hans-Josef Linkens of the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF). Activities related to EOSC that may exist in the sixteen German states have not been accounted for (e.g., [Big Data competence centres](#)⁶⁰ and the [e-Science](#)⁶¹ effort in the state of Baden-Württemberg). The following national organisations have been identified.

2.4.4.1 National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)

In November 2018, the German federal government and the governments of the German states, acting in unity with the Joint Science Conference^{62,63} (GWK), has decided to fund [NFDI](#)⁶⁴, one of the largest scientific state-wide data oriented scientific initiatives. Over three funding rounds, starting with calls for proposals in 2019 and 2020 and accompanied by the DFG, consortia were invited to develop a portfolio of FAIR data services oriented along scientific disciplines or communities. A third call is planned in 2021. The initiative, officially launched in 2020 is registered as legal entity and has a current budget of €900 Million which is secured for ten years. With the goal to bring scientific communities together to eventually provide science-driven data services, the infrastructure also aims to contribute to the development of EOSC and to connect German data infrastructures with European and international platforms. NFDI is mandated member in the EOSC association.

The NFDI consists of a number of consortia which are associations of universities, non-university research institutions, departmental research institutions, academies, and other publicly funded information infrastructure institutions or other corresponding actors. As of this writing 9 consortia are in operation with 18 more awaiting formal approval. Each consortium will develop and offer a service portfolio for research data management for its subarea. Proposals and the consortia of NFDI must comply to the requirement of describing how they will connect with international developments, such as EOSC, and how they plan to ensure compliance with the FAIR principles⁶⁵.

⁶⁰ <https://www.bmbf.de/de/big-data-management-und-analyse-grosser-datenmengen-851.html>

⁶¹ <https://mwk.baden-wuerttemberg.de/de/forschung/forschungslandschaft/e-science>

⁶² <https://www.gwk-bonn.de/en/>

⁶³ German: "Gemeinsame Wissenschaftskonferenz"

⁶⁴ <https://www.dfg.de/foerderung/programme/nfdi>

⁶⁵ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/establishing-fair-data-services>

2.4.4.2 *Helmholtz Data Federation*⁶⁶

The Helmholtz Data Federation (HDF) is a strategic initiative and expansion investment of the Helmholtz Association and addresses the challenges large scale data management in science, in particular data from the large research infrastructures operated by the constituting Helmholtz centres. By using and complementing existing methods and software tools for distributed data management, the computing centres of six Helmholtz centre including the computing centre of EOSC-Pillar partner KIT, form the core of the nationwide research infrastructure HDF. Scientific applications range from polar and marine research, climate research, energy research and health research to photon science and nuclear and particle physics.

2.4.4.3 *Helmholtz Federated IT Services (HIFIS)*⁶⁷

The goal of HIFIS to create a seamless, high-performance, community-wide IT infrastructure in Helmholtz association. To this end, a federated services and cloud-oriented platform is being built on a high-performance network infrastructure, complemented with a federated authentication and authorization infrastructure (AAI). Further services offered are training and support for sustainable software development. EOSC-Pillar partner KIT and ten other Helmholtz centres are involved in HIFIS.

2.4.4.4 *GAIA-X*⁶⁸

The GAIA-X project was initiated by the German Federal Ministries for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi) and for Education and Research (BMBF) with the aim of establishing a networked, high-performance, secure and trustworthy data infrastructure for Europe. The project aims to build a European data ecosystem, especially for business. Soon after its inception 11 French joined the 11 German companies and together moved the project into a AISBL legal entity in 2020. The GAIA-X AISBL currently has over 300 members. The project envisions the networking of decentralized infrastructure services, primarily cloud and edge instances, into a homogeneous, user-friendly system and is organised around the concept of national hubs. With some stretch it is safe to consider GAIA-X as the EOSC counterpart for commercial enterprises.

2.4.5 Italy

In Italy, ICDI (Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure) is the NI chosen as Mandated Organization by the Ministry of University and Research (MUR). It started as a collaboration agreement between main Italian research organisations such as CNR, INFN, ENEA, INAF... with the aim to collaborate in new projects and to coordinate their participation in EOSC. Then when the EOSC-A was first established as a legal entity, ICDI was one of the four founding members. Up to now, the EOSC-A includes 24 Italian organisations (20 members, 3 observers and 1 mandated organisation). Most of them are members of ICDI, but not all, although non-members also have generally shown interest in coordinating with ICDI. ICDI

⁶⁶ <https://www.helmholtz.de/forschung/information-data-science/helmholtz-data-federation-hdf>.

⁶⁷ <https://www.hifis.net/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.data-infrastructure.eu/GAIA-X/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html>

does not have yet a legal form, and it is represented by GARR in this stage. A dedicated TF is working on ICDI legal form and statutes: discussion is ongoing, but there is a general agreement to aim for a lightweight organisation.

ICDI is a bottom-up initiative, and did start from Research Infrastructures, while the University component was joining in a second stage and is growing stronger in this second stage.

Despite relatively frequent changes in the MUR, the relationship with ICDI is stable. The MUR has joined ICDI as an observer since its beginning in 2018. ICDI experts have contributed to draft the Open Science National Plan that will be soon published.

To promote community engagement, ICDI keeps bi-weekly meetings⁶⁹, open not only to ICDI members but also to Italian EOSC members, where matters of EOSC-A are discussed as well as other topics of interest for the Italian community.

The Shadow Task Forces will follow the work of the EOSC Advisory Groups TFs and discuss with the Italian delegates participating in them (following the positive experience of the ICDI Shadow groups that were set up in parallel with the EB WGs in 2019)

The Italian Federated Cloud Platform Task Force (FCP-IT), has the aim to develop a strategy and identify adequate technical solutions to create a federated cloud dedicated to research on a national scale and to propose itself as a model at the European level.

The Italian Competence Centre for EOSC Task Force has the objective to set up a national Competence Centre and a platform to federate, coordinate and further disseminate the existing competences within Research bodies, Infrastructures and Universities that are part of the Italian Open Science community. The TF organises training courses and also a webinar series called 'Open Science Café' to promote the discussion on specific topics related to EOSC.

The Clinical Data Management Task Force aims to build a support platform for the management of clinical data, with a special focus on data related to COVID-19, contributing to the European COVID-19 platform, and creating a Proof of Concept that can be used for sharing biomedical data relating to other pathologies.

Moreover, ICDI is responsible for collecting information on specific topics related to Open Science and EOSC activities, both on its own initiative and in response to requests from the MUR and the Italian delegations in ESFRI and EOSC, with the aim of improving the knowledge of the scenario of Italian research and digital infrastructures.

⁶⁹ See: <https://www.icdi.it/en/activities>

3 Future perspectives in EOSC-Rel

EOSC-Pillar has established strong and institutional relationships with the other regional projects and with the projects that were active in developing the different aspect of EOSC, like EOSC-Enhance and EOSC-Hub. Now EOSC-Future is taking over in many of these activities and EOSC-Pillar has already started working for setting up solid links with it too. It has to be noted that also the AGs, in which as said above EOSC-Pillar is deeply involved will need strong links with the Projects that will work at the EOSC, because the manpower for making the EOSC to evolve on the lines recommended by the AGs will be largely dependent from the financed projects and thus a strong collaboration between the AGs and the present and future financed projects is absolutely needed for getting a viable and efficient EOSC.

4 Conclusions: Final Results and Impact

EOSC-Pillar has till now successfully developed its program on schedule. The EOSC-Rel are integral part of this program not only as far as Task 2.2, responsible for this deliverable, is concerned, but in many other relevant aspects, as described above. EOSC-Pillar as a project and its members have till now given important contributions to the EOSC system, and are now in the position of contributing more and more to the construction of a EOSC really useful and sustainable.